

Evaluation of granular insecticides to control rice root weevil

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In a trial in farmers' fields in Patiala district during the 1979 wet season, eight granular and one emulsifiable concentrate insecticides were evaluated for control of rice root weevil *Echinocnemus oryzae*. The randomized block design used a 33-m² plot size. Granular insecticides were broadcast in paddy water. The emulsifiable concentrate was diluted and sprinkled. Larval populations were counted by uprooting 10 hills/plot immediately before and 10 and 20 days

Effect of granular insecticides on control of rice root weevil, Punjab, India, 1979 wet season.

Insecticide ^a	Larval population reduction ^b (%)	
	10 DAT	20 DAT
Aldrin (Aldrin 30EC)	66.9 ab	84.5 ab
Carbofuran (Furadan 3G)	71.8 a	89.6 a
Disulfoton (Solvirex 5G)	56.6 bc	65.0 c
Fensulfthion (Dasanit 5G)	64.0 abc	63.6 c
Gamma BHC (Lindane 6G)	52.6 a	62.2 c
Isofenphos (Oftanol 5G)	57.0 bc	76.6 ab
Mephosfolan (Cytrolane 5G)	77.3 a	88.4 ab
Phorate (Thimet 10G)	75.6 a	81.2 ab
Quinalphos (Ekalux 5G)	73.8 a	84.9 ab

^aApplied @ 0.75 kg a.i./ha 21 days after transplanting. ^bIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level. DAT = days after treatment.

after treatment (DAT).

At 10 DAT, none of the insecticides had caused more than 80% reduction in larval population (see table). However, carbofuran, mephosfolan, phorate, and quinalphos caused more than 70%

reduction.

At 20 DAT, aldrin, carbofuran, mephosfolan, phorate, and quinalphos had caused more than 80% reduction in larval populations. Isofenphos caused more than 70% reduction. ■

Effect of carbofuran root zone application rate on feeding activity and mortality of the green leafhopper

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Tungro, a serious rice disease, is controlled by planting resistant varieties and by applying insecticides. Incorporating carbofuran in the root zone at planting time generally controls tungro by preventing green leafhopper (*Nephotettix virescens*) feeding. An insectary study was conducted to determine the effect of carbofuran rates on residual activity and feeding of the insect.

Three rates of encapsulated carbofuran 3% granules were inserted into the root zone. Beginning 1 day after application, 10 adult female green leafhoppers were caged over filter paper on the plants at 5-day intervals. Forty-eight hours after infestation, insect mortality was recorded. Feeding activity was determined by measuring the size of purple-stained spots produced by the action of honeydew and ninhydrin on filter papers treated with 0.01% ninhydrin solution.

Although there was substantial feeding at all rates, less feeding activity occurred at the rates of 0.75 and 0.50 kg a.i./ha than in the control until 40 days after treatment (see table). It was observed that the insects kept moving

Residual activity of carbofuran applied in the root zone to control green leafhopper and its effect on insect feeding.^a IRR I insectary, 1980.

Days after treatment	0.75 kg a.i./ha	0.50 kg a.i./ha	0.25 kg a.i./ha	Control
	<i>Insect mortality (%)</i>			
1	90 a	33 b	38 b	0 c
5	100 a	98 a	63 b	0 c
10	100 a	100 a	100 a	0 b
15	100 a	100 a	78 b	0 c
20	95 a	98 a	70 b	0 c
25	90 a	50 b	20 b	0 c
30	80 a	48 b	13 c	0 c
35	68 a	40 b	10 c	3 c
40	65 a	25 b	3 c	3 c
45	30 a	5 ab	0 b	0 b
	<i>Feeding activity (mm²)</i>			
1	106 b	172 b	262 b	625 a
5	60 b	91 b	205 b	540 a
10	44 b	46 b	52 b	623 a
15	34 b	37 b	136 b	626 a
20	46 b	60 b	117 b	637 a
25	115 c	349 c	736 b	978 a
30	173 b	256 b	593 a	669 a
35	177 b	338 b	652 a	641 a
40	210 b	394 b	733 a	641 a
45	438 b	874 a	1079 a	904 a

^aIn a row, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

away from the treated plants, suggesting that the feeding that occurred was limited to a short time. Under field con-

ditions, feeding time on treated plants may be too short to inoculate plants with tungro virus. ■

Fluctuation of yellow stem borer moths in Tirur, India

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The yellow stem borer *Tryporyza incertulas*, a major pest of rice in Chingleput

district of Tamil Nadu, occurs in all three seasons: sornavari (Apr-May to Aug-Sep), samba (Jul-Aug to Nov-Dec), and navarai (Dec-Jan to Apr-May).

Light trap studies were conducted from January 1976 to December 1979 to study the pattern of stem borer occurrence and to find the peak periods of

incidence.

The light trap was fitted with an ordinary tungsten 200-watt bulb in 1976 and 1979 and with an 80-watt mercury vapor lamp in 1977 and 1978. The light was on daily from 1800 to 0600 hours. The daily collection of stem borer moths was recorded.

The data show that first-generation moths were abundant in April-May (see figure). In June and the first fortnight of July, the population declined. From the second fortnight of July, until the end of August, the moths again increased. From September to November, emergence was at its lowest. But moth occurrence increased in December-January. From February to March, moth incidence was low.

In general, three abundant periods — April-May, July-August, and December-January — were noted. These periods synchronized with the productive phase of navarai crops, vegetative

Fluctuation of stem borer moth populations, 1976 to 1979. Tirur, India.

phase of sornavari crops, and productive density was strongly influenced by the phase of samba crops. Evidently moth local rice cropping pattern. ■

Evaluation of commercial and coded insecticides to control brown planthopper and green leafhopper

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One of the most serious problems in insect pest control is insecticide resistance. A countermeasure is the substitution of new insecticides. Continuous screening of newly developed insecticides is conducted in IRRI greenhouses and fields. In 1980, 23 compounds were screened as contact and foliar spray applications in the greenhouse against brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* and green leafhopper *Nephotettix virescens*.

Of the compounds tested, only cypermethrin, dioxacarb, M9918, M10604, NNI-750, UC27867, and UC54229 were effective against the brown planthopper and green leafhopper in Potter's spray tower and foliar application tests (see table). NNI-750, a growth regulator which kills the insect at molting, was effective against nymphs, but had no effect on adults. ■

Effectiveness of insecticides applied in the Potter's spray tower and as foliar spray against brown planthoppers (BPH) and green leafhoppers (GLH). IRRI, 1980.

Insecticide			Application method ^b			
			Potter's spray tower		Foliar spray	
Common name	Formulation	Group ^a	BPH	GLH	BPH	GLH
A-41286	48 EC		-	-	-	+
Agrotin 300	30 EC		-	-	-	-
Cypermethrin	10 EC	Pyrethroid	+	+	+	+
Dioxacarb	50 WP	Carbamate	+	+	+	+
Dioxathion	96 EC	Organophosphate	-	-	-	+
EXP5494	25 EC		+	-	-	-
M9918	20 OE		+	+	+	+
M10604	20 OE		+	+	+	+
Methidathion	40 EC	Organophosphate	-	+	+	+
Methiocarb	50 WP	Carbamate	-	-	+	+
NNI-750	50 WP		+	+	+	+
Pirimiphos methyl + carbophenothion	20 EC	Organophosphate	-	-	+	+
RP-32861	20 EC		+	+	-	-
SAN 285 AD	76 WP		-	-	-	-
SAN 2401	74 WP		-	-	-	-
Trichlorfon	95 SP	Organophosphate	-	-	-	-
U-56295	85 WP		-	-	-	-
U-57770	85 WP		-	-	-	-
UBI-W439-1265	50 WP		-	-	-	-
UC27867	50 WP	Carbamate	+	+	+	+
UC54229	100 Tech.	Carbamate	+	+	+	+
UC/MP 19779	48 EC	Carbamate	-	-	-	+
UC SF-1	40 F	Carbamate	-	+	+	+

^aComposition of several insecticides not available. ^b+ = ≥ 80% mortality 48 hours after spraying with Potter's spray tower and placing insects on foliar-treated plants.